

ERIC Forum 2

Updated ERIC Forum Communications Strategy

Work Package 14 - Deliverable 14.1

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Executive summary

The Second Implementation Project for the ERIC Forum (from now on ERIC Forum 2 or EF2) is born to further structure the cooperation between the ERICs and to support the implementation of the ERICs' policy, shaping their community identity and consolidating their integration within the European Research Area (ERA). It officially started on the 1st of September 2023, thanks to funds from the Horizon Europe Action.

The Project's **main objectives** are

- Provide updated data and information on the ERICs to demonstrate their outcomes, impacts, and importance in the ERA.
- Develop shared practices, regulations, and services to improve ERICs' sustainability and ensure compatibility with European political priorities.
- Strengthen coordination and networking between the ERICs, supporting ERICs-in-preparation.
- Ensure that ERICs have an adequate representation on the European stage, a unified voice to speak with, and strong links with society, economy, and competitiveness.

The Updated ERIC Forum Communications Strategy represents a tool for effectively communicating the project's results. It outlines the objectives, key messages, audience, main instruments, and the timeline of communication activities, representing a guideline to all those involved in building the identity brand of the project. To maintain inner coherence, it is deeply rooted in the plan previously developed during the first project to implement the ERIC Forum.

The strategy defined here will be updated during the entire duration of the ERIC Forum 2, following the fixed deliverables and the outcomes of the work packages dedicated to communication. In general, the Plan will be dedicated to strengthening the sense of common purpose among the ERICs, empowering the brand strategy, mapping the relevant stakeholders, and identifying consistent ways to measure and testify its impact.

Document log

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1. The Updated ERIC Forum Communication Strategy

This revised Communications Strategy is an updated version of two existing documents from the ERIC Forum (EF) implementation project¹:

- ERIC Forum Deliverable 5.1 (ERIC Forum Communication Strategy), originally drafted in April 2019 and updated in September 2021.
- Deliverable 5.2 (ERIC Forum Communication Plan) was published in August 2019.

This Updated ERIC Forum Communications Strategy aims to enhance these two documents, in part driven by the overarching ERIC Forum **objective on communications**, as detailed below:

Support common communication and outreach activities and strengthen external representation of European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) as a stakeholder in consultations and other policy actions that could affect them.

1.1 Key Messages

The key messages of the EF project remain relevant here:

- The ERIC Forum is an important consultation body for science policy related matters.
- The ERIC Forum is a tool for the ERIC community to speak with a unified voice, highlighting its added value to the European science panorama, showcasing its contribution to societal challenges, Horizon Europe Missions and UN SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals), making it a strategic pillar in the European Research Area.
- The ERIC Forum implements and contributes to the discussion on further development of the ERIC Regulation.

1.2 Communication Activities

Communications activities set out in the EF Strategy state:

- Keep the ERIC Forum up to date about the different activities of each ERIC and encourage cooperation on common activities.
- Set-up and manage the appropriate communication tools (e.g., ERIC Forum website, social media accounts, etc.)
- Keep the project's partners and stakeholders informed about the goals and activities of the ERIC Forum.
- Maintain and enforce a two-way dialogue between the members of the ERIC Forum and its stakeholders – research infrastructures, prospective ERICs, EC, ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) and national ministries.

¹ Funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 823798.

- Disseminate project results to the key audiences.
- Develop a publicly available toolbox, which will aid future ERICs in their setting up and early operation phase.

These standard communications activities remain the core ambitions for this revised Strategy.

1.3 Target Audience

The main target audiences from the EF Communication Plan also remain fit for purpose, though these will be enhanced further through in-depth stakeholder mapping exercises for the media and policy as part of EF2.

- Policy makers at the European, national and regional level
- Media organisations, journalists and the general public
- Project partners and bodies
- Research communities in academia (and industry)
- Pan-European Research Infrastructures
- Prospective ERICs from all clusters

Additionally, EF2 identifies the target audiences as:

- Community of European Research Infrastructures, including ESFRI
- Community of current ERICs and ERICs-to-be
- EC, in particular EC- Directorate-General for Research and Innovation; and EP and EU Council
- National Ministries for research
- National Ministries of finances
- Wider stakeholders including universities/academic institutions at international level
- Media
- Citizens

The type of message provided by the communication activities changes in accordance with each type of target. Here is a short list of what the ERIC Forum 2 Project will provide:

Target-driven Key Messages	
Target Audience	Content
Project Partner	The ERIC Forum provides information, best practices, and potential solutions to the challenges ERICs may face from a regulatory perspective. It is also a platform for the exchange of knowledge and opportunities. In other words, being part of the ERIC community is a way to expand one's capabilities and strengthen one's voice in Europe.
ERIC Network	Joining the ERIC community allows one to learn from the experiences, practices, and communities of other ERICs. It provides state-of-the-art regulations and policies aligned with the requirements and updates

	demanded by the European Union. In other words, it allows them to grow and strengthen together.
Politicians and Policy Makers	The ERIC Forum is a consultation body for all EU policies related to research infrastructures, particularly the ERIC regulation. It centralized the challenges ERICs face in this regard and the potential solutions being implemented. Moreover, with its extensive network of RIs in Europe, the ERIC community helps to define the face of European research. It is, therefore, a point of reference for understanding its impact, lines of interest, and peaks of excellence.
Research Communities	The ERIC Forum is a platform that would provide information on the services (such as experiments, possibilities, and the use of data) within different RIs in Europe. It is a knowledge provider on ERICs, their activities, and publications.
Media Agencies	The ERIC Forum is a platform through which the general public can better understand what an RI/distributed RI/ERIC is and the outcomes of such RIs on current research.

1.4 Overarching Objectives

This revised Strategy also sets out to address the overarching objectives set out in the EF2 grant agreement, as detailed below:

ERIC Forum 2 Overarching Objectives	
Internal Communication	
Building on the successful communications activities developed through the EF1 project, WP14-WP16 will focus on strengthening internal communications. This is particularly important since the number of ERICs has increased considerably since the first edition of the project. It is therefore necessary to strengthen internal coordination to ensure that the Forum has a unified voice. WP14-16 will also deliver opportunities for the ERIC Forum and individual ERICs to attain positive external engagement with external stakeholders (in the media, policy arenas, and the general public). Internal communications efforts will engage new ERICs within the project, strengthen the ERIC Forum brand strategy, and facilitate a sense of common purpose and support for each other. This will enable ERIC communications teams to individually and collectively develop and share best practices, skills and training.	
External Communication	
Focusing on external communications will help ERICs individually and collectively identify media and policy opportunities by mapping relevant stakeholders, understanding how to develop news content and sharing success stories. There will also be a focus on identifying consistent ways to measure impact.	

Additionally, arguably most ambitiously, the ERIC Forum brings together some of the world's largest and most innovative collaborative science projects. Within the Forum are experts across all scientific disciplines, particularly concerning policy announcements, collaborative science projects and funding opportunities. This

Strategy should, therefore, aim **to position the ERIC Forum as *the* authoritative source to comment on scientific developments**. It should, in effect, become one of the largest scientific lobbying organisation in Europe, offering well-briefed spokespeople to comment on scientific announcements and developments in the media at European and national level.

This Strategy sets out how EF2 project partners – collectively and individually – can develop content to be promoted via existing and new channels of communication – internal, online and external – to communicate more effectively to target audiences.

1.5 Visual and Identity Narratives

The following texts shape the brand identity narrative of the project. They are a short and effective reference to describe the project and its primary goals. Hence, they will be used as a guideline to produce material useful for media needing information on ERIC Forum 2. The texts were conceived while drafting the first strategy plan for ERIC Forum 1. Where necessary, they were adapted for the second edition of the project.

Mission
ERIC Forum
The ERIC Forum aims to advance the operations of ERICs and contribute to strategically developing ERIC-related policies.
ERIC Forum 2 Project
The Second Implementation Project for the ERIC Forum brings together the ERIC community to strengthen its coordination and collaboration. The strategic approach of the ERIC Forum will continue to address critical challenges and develop best practices.

Project Scope and Vision
ERIC Forum 2 Project
The Second Implementation Project for the ERIC Forum aims to strengthen the coordination within the ERIC community and enhance collaboration between partners. The strategic approach of the ERIC Forum will contribute to addressing critical challenges, developing best practices, and framing the necessary knowledge to support ERICs-to-be with various aspects. Moreover, this will contribute to building the brand identity of ERICs as an important body and stakeholder in consultation with related policy action.

The visual identity manual from EF remains fit for purpose and is available [here](#).

1.6 Horizon Europe Rules

Following articles 17.2 and 17.3 from GRANT AGREEMENT 101124559, all project partners must implement the following statements for the communication activities related to the project.

Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment, and major results funded by the grant must:

- Display the EU emblem.
- Include the following texts: “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”
- When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

2. Developing Content: The Communication Plan

Significant resources need to be spent on developing news content. This is a key task that initially requires the review of the EF2 grant agreement and population of a comprehensive schedule. This should draw on the list of deliverables and direct communication between the EF2 communications team and work package leaders. This plan should clearly set out:

- Timetable
- Action (related initially to deliverables, but direct communication may add to this)
- Responsibility (should always include the communications team)
- News angle (type and perspective of the news)
- Liaison (project partner with responsibility for the work)
- Target audience(s)
- Channel(s) of communication

Each work package should initially be reviewed for reportable content to achieve this. Not all deliverables will be relevant for reporting, but the review should establish this. As part of this, we strongly suggest using the SharePoint created by the Project Coordinator (BBMRI) to reduce the burden of deliverable authors and ensure that the communications team is aware of all project activity.

The first version of this communications plan can be found in Appendix III. This will be a ‘live’ document, continuously reviewed and, where appropriate, updated throughout the project. It includes all regular mailings – internally and externally – and all deliverables and milestones (listed in their delivery month). Additionally, it indicates when the communications team should contact those responsible for submitting deliverables to discuss dissemination activities (added three months before deliverable due dates). In this initial contact phase, the required information for each communications activity should be completed.

2.1 Spokespeople

Project partners should be approached to become authoritative spokespeople on each of the major ERIC domains (Energy, Environment, Health and Food, Physical Science and Engineering, and Social and Cultural Innovation). The communications team would then be able to comment on relevant scientific policy announcements, primarily to the media and policy audiences.

These spokespeople should additionally be in position to discuss policy papers developed through the project, notably MS6.1 (general position, white paper, of the EF) and D6.1 (develop a plan for sustainable alignment of the ERIC's policy priorities). With clear objectives, these spokespeople can lobby for the recommended outcomes.

Spokespeople should also be able to use the tools developed through D6.3 (a suite of storytelling content will be produced containing case studies demonstrating success stories) to further promote the impacts of the EF and individual ERICs in an informed way.

The communication team will train spokespersons in communication skills, when necessary.

2.2 Spotlight

One area of producing content could be to focus on each of the EF2 project partners. This type of content was facilitated somewhat in a series of short videos that were produced for the [EF YouTube channel](#). The communications team could ask each project partner to respond to a series of consistent questions about the work their infrastructure undertakes. A series of articles (at least 10) could be published on the EF website and promoted on social media channels.

3. Channels of Communication

3.1 Internal Communications

There is currently a lack of information about EF2 amongst project partners. This should be addressed by a bi-monthly email updating partners about the latest project activities. This will also allow the communications team to request information more easily and offer a straightforward way for project partners to contact the communications team.

Moreover, short guidelines should be produced by the communication team to spread among the Partners with the double aim of optimising and alignment the project communication. The guidelines should include general indications on how each partner can contribute to media coverage meetings, events, or webinars that concern the ERIC Forum (i.e. how many photos and videos take, with which format, etc.) and which type of information are needed by the communication team to properly disseminate news and outcomes. To this end, using the Toolkit available on the ERIC Forum website is highly recommended.

3.2 Online Communications

Several communication channels established during EF should be maintained and enhanced. Whilst public-facing, these are channels in which the EF2 communications team have full editorial control.

The [EF website](#) is the main channel of communication for the project. The content plan developed and suggestions outlined in section 2 of this Strategy should enhance the news section. All news, events and

limited updates to the website should be communicated across the established social media channels. This includes [LinkedIn](#) and [X \(formerly Twitter\)](#).

Additionally, project partners should be encouraged to promote key outputs and news from the project through their own channels, particularly via their websites, social media accounts, newsletters and any other relevant communications channels they have at their disposal.

Existing social media channels should be updated more regularly. This can be achieved through the re-posting of project partners' individual accounts². A possible list of contents that can be shared are job opportunities, workshops and seminars, events or news that concern the ERIC Forum. Lists of key target policy and media audiences should also be established, and a more systematic following strategy, to bring in more followers across both channels. The LinkedIn icon should be added to the EF website.

3.3 External Communications

The quarterly newsletter should promote content created for the EF website and for the promotion of ERICs within the project. It should highlight the work and expertise of the project team. A link to sign up for the newsletter should be more prominently positioned on the EF website. The newsletter should also be another tool to strengthen the ties among the Partners. To this end, it might be useful to include a section with job opportunities that partners can report on and request to be included.

Webinars for key project outputs should be considered (we suggest at least 4, one per project's pillar). These would help position EF2 as *the* authoritative source on scientific projects and, in turn, offer regular content for the website and social media content – both to promote the event in advance and subsequent recordings. This would also help establish an increased presence and external interest in its [YouTube channel](#).

Key media organisations should be identified and approached regularly. Ahead of the formal media mapping exercise (see section 5, below), a shortlist of scientific media publications should be created with named contacts. The EF2 communications team should build relationships and regularly contact those identified to discuss news content and input to wider scientific news.

The use of the [Research Infrastructure Communicators Slack channel](#) developed through the Research Infrastructures Visibility (RI-VIS) project that ended in 2021 should be encouraged. This channel of communication is not updated regularly, but it does have more than 600 members and offers a channel to communications teams both within and beyond project partners in the scientific community.

4. Increasing Audience

As part of the drafting of this Strategy, two stakeholder mapping exercises will be implemented to help EF2 project partners – collectively and individually – target media and policy audiences more effectively.

² See Annex II for a list of all the Partners with their social media accounts. In Annex III it is possible to find useful hashtag that can be used. [ERIC Forum's Toolkit](#) has been used to define part of the hashtag.

The first of these will be the development of a database that includes contact information for stakeholders from the European policy arena. The database will initially identify government departments of relevance to each of the major ERIC types (energy, environment, health and food, physical science and engineering, and social and cultural innovation). It will include contact details for policy makers at the Commission and at the national level. Once the mapping exercise is complete, this resource will be made available across ERICs, with space to include feedback of contact attempts, highlighting examples of successful pathways to impact. This will be compiled as part of WP14.

In a similar exercise to the one outlined above, stakeholder mapping will be undertaken for the European media landscape. This will focus on media outlets who report on the European Commission/Parliament and research focused publications' activities. This will also include journalists who cover these issues in more traditional national and international media organisations and trade press specific to each of the major ERIC types. This mapping exercise will be undertaken in WP15.

These mapping exercises will be key to positioning the EF as the authoritative source for major scientific policy and funding announcements.

5. Impact Indicators

Regarding impact, this Strategy suggests distinguishing between:

- **Action index**, i.e. how many communication actions were taken. This category includes the number of articles and news items, posts on social channels, multimedia products, webinars, newsletters, brochures (or guidelines) realised.
- **Reception index**, i.e. how much of the public was engaged by these communication actions. Here, it is suggested to look at website visitors, the trend of followers and newsletter subscribers, the number of views on social media and the YouTube channel, and the type of engagement (from likes to comments and reactions to the attention span on the singular video).
- **Effectiveness index**, i.e. how well communication conveys the intended message. We suggest applying the latter to evaluating the guidelines and the internal communication materials, with the twofold aim of ensuring that they are useful products for the Forum and obtaining suggestions for future project editions.

The table below outlines these three different indices that WP16 will implement.

Impact Indices
Action Index
Number of news published on the website

Number of posts (distinguishing between original posts and reposts from other accounts)
Numbers of videos
Editions of the bimonthly newsletter sent
Editions of the quarterly newsletter sent
Number of webinars realized
Reception Index
Number and trend of the followers on the social media accounts
Number and type of engagement (likes, comments, reactions, etc.)
Number and trend of the newsletter subscribers
Number and trend on the YouTube Channel
The attention span for the different videos
Number of participants in the online events
Effectiveness Index
Survey or Focus Groups inside the ERIC Forum's community

6. Annex

6.1 Annex I - List of the Partners with their Social Media Contacts

ERIC Forum 2 Partners			
Name	Abbreviation	X	LinkedIn
Biobanks And Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure Consortium	BBMRI-ERIC	@BBMRIERIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bbmri-eric/
Analysis And Experimentation on Ecosystem ERIC	AnaEE ERIC	@AnaEE_EU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/anaee-analysis-and-experimentation-on-ecosystems/
Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium	CERIC-ERIC	@CERICnews	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ceric-eric/
CESSDA ERIC	CESSDA ERIC	@CESSDA_Data	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cessda/
CLARIN ERIC	CLARIN ERIC	@CLARINERIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/clarin-eric/
Digital Research Infrastructure for The Arts and Humanities	DARIAH ERIC	@DARIAHeu	https://www.linkedin.com/company/dariah-eric/
EATRIS ERIC	EATRIS	@EatrisEric	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eatris-eric/
ECCSEL European Research Infrastructure Consortium	ECCSEL ERIC	@ECCSEL_ERIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eccsel/
ECRIN European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network	ECRIN	@ECRIN_ERIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ecrin/
Extreme Light Infrastructure ERIC	ELI ERIC	@ELI_laser	/
European Marine Biological Research Centre ERIC	EMBRC-ERIC	@EMBRC_EU	https://www.linkedin.com/company/embrc/

European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and Water Column Observatory ERIC	EMSO ERIC	@EMSOeu	https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-multidisciplinary-seafloor-and-water-column-observatory/
European Plate Observing System ERIC	EPOS ERIC	@EPOSeu	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eposeu/
European Social Survey ERIC	ESS ERIC	@ESS_Survey	https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-social-survey/
City University of London	CITY	@CityUniLondon	https://www.linkedin.com/school/city-university-london/
European Infrastructure of Open Screening Platform for Chemical Biology ERIC	EU-OS	@EuOpenscreen	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eu-openscreen/
EURO-ARGO ERIC	EURO-ARGO ERIC	@EuroArgoERIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/euro-argo-eric/
EURO-BIOIMAGING ERIC	EURO-BIOIMAGING	@EuroBioImaging	https://www.linkedin.com/company/euro-bioimaging/
European Spallation Source ERIC	ESS Spallation	@essneutron	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ess-neutron/
Integrated Carbon Observation System ERIC	ICOS ERIC	@ICOS_CP	https://www.linkedin.com/company/integrated-carbon-observation-system/
INSTRUCT-ERIC	INSTRUCT-ERIC	@instructhub	https://www.linkedin.com/company/instruct-eric/
Joint Institute for Very Long Baseline Interferometry as ERIC	JIV-ERIC	@jivevbi	https://www.linkedin.com/company/jivevbi/
E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research	LIFEWATCH ERIC	@LifeWatchERI	https://www.linkedin.com/company/lifewatch-eric/
European Research Infrastructure Consortium for the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe	SHARE ERIC	@SHARE_MEA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/share-survey-of-health-ageing-and-retirement-in-europe/
ERIC Forum 2 Affiliated Entities			
Szkola Glowna Handlowa w Warszawie	SGH	@SGHWarsaw	https://www.linkedin.com/school/sgh-warsaw-school-of-economics/
Share Berlin Institute GMBH	SBI	/	

6.2 Annex II - List of Useful Hashtags

ERIC Forum 2 Useful Hashtags
For General Use – ERIC Forum
#ERICForum #ERICs @SDGs
For General Use
#EU_RIs #ResearchInfrastructure #Policy4Science
To Communicate Cutting-Edge Services, Facilities and Resources
#makesciencehappen
To Communicate Research Advancements, Big Science and Big Results
#RIimaginescience

6.3 Annex III – The Communication Plan

Below is the first version of this Communications Plan.

MONTH	ACTION	RESPONSIBILITY	NEWS ANGLE	LIAISON	TARGET AUDIENCE	CHANNEL(S)
March 2024	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	Address ERIC Regulation challenges (D12.1)	Comms team	Best practice	Euro-Argo	Project partners	
April 2024	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
May 2024	Discuss D7.1 dissemination plans	Comms team		Instruct	Project partners, RIs	Email
June 2024	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
July 2024						

August 2024	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
	Best practice guide for engagement with Third Countries (D7.1)	Comms team		Instruct	Project partners, RIs	
September 2024	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
October 2024	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
	Discuss D9.1 dissemination plans	Comms team	Events	EATRIS		Email
	Discuss D11.1 dissemination plans	Comms team		CERIC	Project partners	Email
November 2024	Discuss D4.2 dissemination plans	Comms team		ECRIN		Email
	Discuss D5.2 dissemination plans	Comms team		EURO BIOIMAGING		Email
	Discuss D7.2 dissemination plans	Comms team		Instruct		Email
	Discuss D9.2 dissemination plans	Comms team		ESS (SE)		Email

December 2024	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
	Discuss D5.1 dissemination plans	Comms team		Euro-Argo	Policy	Email
January 2025						
February 2025	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
	Launch of Stakeholder Engagement Plan (D4.2)	Comms team		ECRIN		
	Revision of European Charter of Access to Research Infrastructures (D5.2)	Comms team	Policy recommendation	EURO BIOIMAGING	Policy	
	Cooperation activities with the international organisations (D7.2)	Comms team	Events	Instruct	Project partners	Website, webinar
	Webinar programme on gender equality (D9.1)	Comms team	Events	EATRIS		Website, webinar
	Toolbox to support ERIC engagement with industry (D9.2)	Comms team	Launch	ESS (SE)	Project partners	

	Employment regulations (D11.1)	Comms team		CERIC	Project partners	
March 2025	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	ERIC sustainability policy paper (D5.1)	Comms team	Policy recommendation	Euro-Argo	Policy	
	Recommendations for the revision of the European Charter of Access to Research Infrastructures (5.2)	Comms team	Policy recommendation			
April 2025	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
May 2025						
June 2025	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All		
July 2025	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email

August 2025						
September 2025	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
October 2025	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
November 2025						
December 2025	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All		
January 2026						

February 2026	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
March 2026	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
April 2026	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
	Discuss D9.4 dissemination plans	Comms team	Best practice	BBMRI	Project partners	Email
May 2026	Discuss D2.1 dissemination plans	Comms team		DARIAH, ICOS	Project partners	Email
	Discuss MS4.1/D4.1 dissemination plans	Comms team		EMSO	Policy	Email
	Discuss MS6.1/MS6.2 dissemination plans	Comms team	Policy recommendation	EURO BIOIMAGING	Policy	Email
	Discuss D8.1 dissemination plans	Comms team		ELI		Email
	Discuss D12.2 dissemination plans	Comms team		Euro-Argo		Email
	Discuss D12.3 dissemination plans	Comms team		ELI	Policy	Email
	Discuss D15.1 dissemination plans	Comms team	Best practice	BBMRI	Project partners	Email

June 2026	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
	Discuss D6.2 dissemination plans	Comms team		EU OPENSREEN		Email
	Discuss D11.2 dissemination plans	Comms team	Policy recommendation	CERIC	Policy	Email
July 2026	Discuss D8.2 dissemination plans	Comms team	Innovative	LifeWatch		Email
	Discuss D9.3 dissemination plans	Comms team	Data protection	ESS Social	Project partners	Email
	News and media skills capacities across the Ris (D9.4)	Comms team	Best practice	BBMRI	Project partners	Email
August 2026	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All		
	Launch of reporting platform (D2.1)	Comms team		DARIAH, ICOS		Website, social, newsletter, launch event?
	Success stories of ERIC involvement in Horizon Europe outside Pillar 1 (MS4.1)	Comms team	Best practice	EMSO		Website
	ERICs engagement in Horizon Europe (D4.1)	Comms team	Best practice	EMSO	Policy	Website, social, newsletter
	EF general position paper (MS6.1)	Comms team	Policy recommendation	EURO BIOIMAGING	Policy	Website
	National funding landscape analysis (MS6.2)	Comms team	Best practice	EURO BIOIMAGING		Website
	White book on Green and Digital transition of ERICs (D8.1)	Comms team	Innovative	ELI	Policy, media	

	Implementation of ERIC Regulation (D12.2)	Comms team	Best practice	Euro-Argo	Policy	
	Implementation of VAT exemption (D12.3)	Comms team	Best practice	ELI	Policy	
	Approaches to reach media targets (D15.1)	Comms team	Best practice	BBMRI	Project partners	Newsletter
Month	Action	Source	News angle	Liaison	Target audience	Channel(s)
September 2026	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	Identified sustainable information channels with the national funding bodies and on performed activities to enhance ERICs visibility in National arenas (D6.2)	Comms team	Innovative	EU OPENSREEN		
	Framework and definition of possible legislative initiatives (D11.2)	Comms team	Policy recommendation	CERIC	Policy	
October 2026	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
	Best Practices: Privacy and Data Protection (D9.3)	Comms team	Data protection	ESS Social	Project partners, Ris	
November 2026	ERICs as catalysts of green and digital transition (D8.2)	Comms team	Innovative	LifeWatch	Media	

December 2026	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
January 2027						
February 2027	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
March 2027	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	Discuss D10.1 dissemination plans	Comms team	Best practice	ELI	Project partners	Email
April 2027	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email

May 2027	Discuss D6.1 dissemination plans	Comms team		EURO BIOIMAGING		Email
	Discuss D6.3 dissemination plans	Comms team		BBMRI	All	
	Discuss D16.1 dissemination plans	Comms team	Best practice	ESS Social	Project partners, RIs	Newsletter
June 2027	Quarterly newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	Internal newsletter	Newsletter recipients	Mailchimp
	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
	Framework for Shared Services (D10.1)	Comms team	Best practice	ELI	Project partners	
July 2027						
August 2027	Internal newsletter	Comms team	Compilation	All	Project partners	Email
	User/sustainability guide for reporting platform (D3.1 / D3.2)	Comms team		DARIAH, ICOS	Project partners, RIs	
	Sustainable alignment of ERIC policy priorities (D6.1)	Comms team		EURO BIOIMAGING		
	Success stories highlighting ERICs' policy and scientific impact (D6.3)	Comms team		BBMRI	All	
	Relevant communications KPIs (D16.1)	Comms team	Best practice	ESS Social	Project partners, RIs	Newsletter